

Long-term composition of 16S-based bacterial communities associated with algal bloom events in northern Chile

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Abstract

There is an increasing interest in how harmful algal blooms affect seawater desalination plants. These plants are critical for supplying municipal drinking water in many arid regions. Blooms can increase the probability of clogging filters, which in turn can disrupt proper plant operations, resulting in temporary shutdowns. Changes in bacterial diversity can be used as predictors of localized algae blooms. In this work, we used high-throughput DNA sequence analyses to study bacterial diversity focused on an event of *Akashiwo sanguinea* bloom in December 2019 on the coast of Antofagasta, Chile, where desalination plants are located. We collected weekly samples of attached-algae bacteria (1.0 µm filter) and free-living bacteria (0.2 µm filter) offshore in Antofagasta city between November 2019 and January 2020. DNA was extracted from the samples and the resulting 16s RNA sequence diversity determined. The resulting data was used to compute alpha diversity indices, Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA), dendrograms, and community composition. We found the relative abundance of attached Cyanobacteria strongly decreased during the bloom whereas Epsilonproteobacteria increased in abundance. Also, relevant functions decreased in blooming in the free-living bacteria.

Keywords: high-throughput DNA, *Akashiwo sanguinea*, algae bloom, bacterial diversity, desalination plants

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Introduction

There is an increasing interest in harmful algal blooms (HAB) affecting seawater desalination plants. In northern Chile, most plants supply drinking and municipal water. Localized HAB can affect the plant operation, leading to temporary shutdown and changing the HAB holobiome diversity.

Facing the problems of increasing industrial and municipal water demand in arid zones, desalination plants are the main solution. This industry is growing with almost 21,000 projects in over 180 countries (Eke, 2020). These seawater desalination plants can be adversely impacted by harmful algae blooms (HAB) in several ways. For blooms of non-toxin species, the most common issue involves high biomass concentration clogging the desalination membranes. Another major issue is the production of hydrogen sulfide when these blooms decay and the resulting biological oxygen demand reduces oxygen concentrations below 0.5 mg L⁻¹. When hydrogen sulfide rich water is taken into the desalination plant, it readily crosses the processing membranes causing the processed water to have a strong rotten egg smell (Anderson, 2017). When this happens, plant operations have to be suspended until the issue can be resolved, leading to significant hardship for the affected community and increased expenses for plant operations. When toxic blooms occur, toxins released into the water as cells die during the water purification process can also enter the water supply again, leading to a suspension of operations when these toxins are detected. Early detection of both toxic and nontoxic blooms in order to allow desalination plants to take preventive actions (Galán, 2020).

The relation between *A. sanguinea* bloom and bacterial community was recently studied in an indoor environment (Jung, 2021). Changes in bacteria abundance were described in three different groups: during, late, post bloom stages. The Flavobacteria and Gammaproteobacteria are active in the three stages decreasing in late bloom and then increasing in post bloom. Moreover, Alphaproteobacteria is abundant in the bloom phase expecting phototropic genera in the algae riosphere as Rhodobacterias (Li, 2019).

Our main goal is to understand changes in bacterial diversity in a HABs in a coastal scenario comparing attached and free-living bacteria in an *A. sanguinea* bloom in December 2019 in Antofagasta, Chile. This information will help to understand the bacterial diversity before the *A. sanguinea* HAB for keeping water supply and avoid plant clogging.

Material and Methods

Study site

Seawater samples were collected weekly by ship about 100 m offshore south of Antofagasta, Chile (Lat -23.68248, Lon -70.41597), located ~20 km south of the desalination plant.

Sampling

The samples were collected between November 15th, 2019 and January 16th, 2020. The measured parameters included water temperature, salinity, cell concentrations of *A. sanguinea* and Chl *a*. To get the DNA sample, 200 mL of seawater was filtered for 16S-rRNA and 18S-Rrna. In the case of particles, filtering must continue. To separate

free-living and attached bacteria, a tandem filtration is performed with a 1 μm pore-size connected to 0.2 μm pore-sized Sterivex membrane. For 18S-Rna, it uses a single filtration with a 0.2 μm Sterivex membrane (Yarimizu, 2020).

We use high-throughput DNA sequence analyses to study the diversity of alga-associated bacteria (attached and free living) focused on an event of *A. sanguinea* bloom in December 2019 on the coast of Antofagasta, Chile, where desalination plants are located. We considered weekly data from Nov. 2019 to Jan. 2020 in two locations.

Metagenomic data

Each water sample was sequenced in the NGS MiSeq-Illumina 3500 Genetic Analyzer, Applied Biosystems, U.S.A.

Data Analysis

Using QIIME2, we computed alpha diversity indices for previous HAB events (PRE) and during the event (HAB), including Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA), and Venn Diagram. Moreover, we search for relevant functions and the dendrogram relating to the samples PRE, HAB, and POST.

Results and Discussion

Taxonomy and bacterial composite

We found that attached *Cyanobacteria* relative abundance changes during the HAB bloom and *Epsilonproteobacteria* increase in abundance. Free bacteria have minor changes in relative abundance with an increase in *Epsilonproteobacteria*.

Relevant functions

From the Faprotax analysis, the attached bacteria relevant functions are chemoheterotrophy, fermentation, and nitrate reduction in the PRE stage, which decrease in the HAB stage. In the case of free-living bacteria, relevant functions are mainly chemoheterotrophy and intracellular parasites followed in a small scale by fermentation, methanol oxidation, methylotrophy, and nitrate reduction. Indeed, chemoheterotrophy and intracellular parasites decrease five weeks before the HAB reaches its minimum, and then increase slowly in the following weeks.

In figure 2, we noticed from the attached bacteria that green samples and yellow samples are close to red samples related to HAB. In the case of the free-living bacteria, we started with yellow samples (PRE) changing to red samples (HAB), and finally the green samples (POST). Check the ordered sample numbering.

Based on our analysis, we detected higher changes in the relative abundances of attached bacteria during PRE and HAB, compared with free-living bacteria. We also found bacterial taxa, which are shared during the long term in analyzed samples. More studies are required to understand the changes and influence of holobiomes in the development of HAB in northern Chile and on its impact on seawater desalination plants.

Fig. 1. Relative abundance, Venn plots, and PCoA of PRE and HAB stages for attached and free-living bacteria.

Fig. 2. Dendrograms of attached (up) and free-living (down) bacteria separating by stages: PRE (yellow), HAB (red), POST (green).

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